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Test of Mycelium Growth Rate and Production Level of White Oyster Mushroom (*Pleurotus Ostreatus*) Using Rice Bran, Corn Bran, Wheat Bran, and Sago Flour

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Abstract

White oyster mushrooms are an agricultural product that has a high nutritional content compared to other mushrooms. White oyster mushrooms have the following nutritional values: 27% protein, 1.6% fat, 58% carbs, 11.5% fiber, 9.3% ash, and 265 calories. One of the commodities that the public is presently requesting in order to satisfy their eating demands is oyster mushrooms. Planting mediums such as sawdust, rice bran, straw, husks, and rice flour are typically utilized to cultivate oyster mushrooms. Finding out how rice bran, maize bran, wheat bran, and sago flour applied optimally affected the white oyster mushroom mycelium development rate and yield was the main goal of this study. The study was conducted in Jasne Kumbung, Guntung Manggis street No. 47, Guntung Manggis Village, Landasan Ulin District, Banjarbaru City, South Kalimantan, from December 2023 to March 2024. With four treatments and four replications, this study used a single component Randomized Block Design (CRD) to produce 20 experimental units. The utilization of rice bran, corn bran, wheat bran, and sago starch was shown to have an impact on the rate of mycelium development and production levels of white oyster mushrooms. The best treatment for the average growth rate of perfect mycelium is sago flour treatment (P_4), the average initial appearance of the first mushroom fruiting body and the average number of clumps per baglog is wheat bran treatment (P_1), mushroom fruit growth and fruit wet weight The best treatment for oyster mushrooms is wheat bran (P_3).

Keywords: mycelium, white oyster mushroom, bran

Introduction

Compared to other mushrooms, white oyster mushroom is an agricultural product that has high nutritional value. According to Cahyana *et al.* (1997), white oyster mushrooms have the following nutritional values: 27% protein, 1.6% fat, 58% carbohydrate, 11.5% fiber, 9.3% ash, and 265 calories. A myriad of health benefits from this mushroom, in addition to its high nutritional content. The cholesterol-free vegetable protein contained, helps avoid the development of hypertension and *heart disease* (Pasaribu *et al.*, 2002). The commodity that people are currently interested in to fulfill their food needs is oyster mushrooms. The fact that demand increases every year shows this. The demand for oyster mushrooms is still high and most of them are still imported from outside the region. Therefore, the maintenance of oyster mushrooms is very necessary (Fritz *et al.*, 2017).

Based on BPS data (2017) in Indonesia, mushrooms consumed were 47,753 tons, compared to production of only 37,020 tons. As much as 10% of the demand for oyster mushrooms increases annually to meet the

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demand for lodging facilities, eating places, vegans, and other consumers (Kalsum *et al.*, 2011). Consumer demand continues to increase, but processed oyster mushrooms are still relatively low (Karisman, 2015). Sawdust is one of the growing media used to raise this mushroom. The maintenance of white oyster mushrooms does not require a large initial investment. According to Suprpti (2000), white oyster mushrooms can be cultivated in a low-tech way and planting media from wood sawdust. Sawdust is easily obtained from the remnants of the woodworking industry.

Nutrients required for oyster mushroom fertility such as lignin, carbohydrates (cellulose and glucose), protein, nitrogen, fiber, and vitamins can be found in the cultivation medium, namely sawdust. Sawdust, rice bran, straw, husks, and rice flour are typical growing media used for oyster mushroom cultivation. According to research by Winarni (2002), the processed results of white oyster mushrooms (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) show that the growing media used based on the best formulation is 15 kg wood sawdust, 2.25 kg rice bran, 0.15 kg plaster, 0.375 kg lime. Mushroom producers face several challenges in sourcing their ingredients. Profit margins will be greatly affected by brand prices. In mushroom cultivation, bra has a crucial function. Mushroom fertility is facilitated by the nutrients found in bran. As a source of carbohydrates, C, and N, bran is added to the growth medium to increase its nutritional value (Cahyana *et al.*, 1997).

Only a few researchers have used different forms of bran. Most research on the productivity of white oyster mushrooms only uses two types of bran with a certain ratio or dose of nutrients. Different types of bran are needed in order to obtain the test results of mycelium growth rate and production level of white oyster mushrooms. This leads the research to find out the rate of mycelium development and the level of yield of white oyster mushrooms using sago flour, rice bran, corn bran, and wheat bran.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research was conducted at Jasne Barn on Guntung Manggis Street No. 47, Guntung Manggis Village, Landasan Ulin District, Banjarbaru City from December 2023 to March 2024. Sawdust, rice bran, wheat bran, corn bran, sago starch, lime, molasses, white oyster mushroom seeds (*Pleurotus ostreatus*), alcohol, plastic, baglog rings, ring caps, rubber bands, and newspapers were the materials used in this study. Hoes, shovels, paddles, mushroom bag presses, sterilization drums, gas stoves, bunsen lamps, drum tubes, hoses, cameras, stationery, scales, hygrometers, and thermometers are some of the equipment used in this study.

This study used a single-factor completely randomized design (CRD) with four levels of P1 (rice bran), P2 (wheat bran), P3 (corn bran), and P4 (sago starch). The implementation of the study began with the preparation of the barn, preparation of planting media, media mixing, media composting, packaging, media sterilization, media cooling, inoculation, incubation, growth, maintenance, and harvesting. The observations made were the growth rate of the perfect mycelium, the beginning of the first mushroom body (*pinhead*), the growth rate of the fungus, the number of clumps per baglog, and the wet weight of the oyster mushroom fruit body.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Perfect Mycelium Growth Rate

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After the seeds were inoculated into the white oyster mushroom baglog media, the use of different types of bran affected the rate of development of perfect mycelium of white oyster mushroom, according to the findings of ANOVA analysis of variance. The treatment of sago starch (P4) showed the fastest average rate of development of complete mycelium of white oyster mushroom with an average of 32.20, the treatment of corn bran (P2) gave the same result. With an average growth rate of 48.40, wheat bran treatment (P3) showed the longest growth rate of complete mycelium of white oyster mushroom.

The appearance of mycelium, the growth rate of mycelium is measured. This is due to the ease of mycelium growth in the presence of organic matter. Carbon from organic sources is used by oyster mushrooms to break down carbon into simple carbon compounds, which are then incorporated into the mycelium to help mycelial growth. Mycelial growth rate tends to increase along with the increase in the amount of sago starch in the medium. This is thought to be due to the high N content in the medium caused by the high levels of sago starch. Oyster mushroom mycelium requires nitrogen to thrive. Oyster mushroom mycelium can develop faster when N is added (Nawaruddin *et al.*, 2017).

Beginning of First Mushroom Fruit Body Appearance

The findings of ANOVA analysis of variance showed that the use of several types of bran affected the formation of the first mushroom fruiting body after the seeds were injected into the white oyster mushroom baglog media. Rice bran treatment (P1) showed the fastest average development of the first white oyster mushroom body with an average of 40.40; corn bran treatment (P2) and sago starch (P4) also had a similar impact. Wheat bran treatment (P3) had the longest average time of first body appearance at 57.80.

Bran serves as a source of protein and carbohydrates when used in combination with planting soil. Protein is required for fruiting body development and enzyme production, while carbohydrates are the main source of energy. White oyster mushrooms obtain their nutrients during growth and development by secreting enzymes that break down lignin, cellulose, and hemicellulose into simple sugars. Laccase (Lac), manganese peroxidase (MnP), and lignin peroxidase (LiP) are some of these enzymes. Fruit bodies are formed using these basic sugars (Maula *et al.*, 2018).

The nutritional content of mushroom growing media that is suitable for the growth and development of mushrooms is often one of the factors that influence the growth of white oyster mushrooms. Fungal fruiting bodies will develop faster the more bran is used as a treatment, because there are various variables that can affect the rapid growth of fruiting bodies in a growing medium, including pH, moisture content, nutrients, and fungal seeds. The initial development of mushroom fruiting bodies is strongly influenced by the addition of bran and sago starch doses to the media. Because bran contains only a small amount of nutrients, adding a small dose will cause the fruiting body to develop more slowly (Syawal *et al.*, 2018).

Mushroom Fruit Growth Rate

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Differences in the use of bran types had an impact on the rate of white oyster mushroom fruit development, according to the findings of the ANOVA analysis of variance. With an average of 3.20, the rice bran treatment (P3) showed the fastest average mushroom fruit growth; similar results were also seen in the treatments of rice bran (P1), corn bran (P2), and sago starch (P4).

Colonization of the substratum and the types of hydrolytic and oxidative enzymes produced have been shown to be significantly affected by the types of nutrient concentrations and supplements. Since *L. edodes* grows rapidly when wheat bran is incorporated, it was found that mycelial development correlates with nitrogen bioavailability. The process by which edible fungi use the ligno-cellulosic substrate in insoluble wheat bran is related to the synthesis of enzymes such as cellulase, hemicellulase, and ligninase, which cause the macro-components of the substrate, cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin, to be hydrolyzed and provide enough low molecular weight nutrients necessary for the growth of the mold. To promote mold development and production, it is important to add supplements to the substrate, especially substrates with low protein content (Sajid *et al.*, 2018).

Number of Clumps Per Baglog

ANOVA analysis of variance showed that the number of clumps per baglog varied according to the type of bran used. The rice bran treatment (P1) showed the highest average number of clumps per baglog with an average of 10.40; the rice bran treatment (P2) showed the same result. This is because the content of nutrients and energy in oyster mushroom media is available and balanced. The development of oyster mushrooms requires a variety of sources of nutrients and energy. Mushrooms need nitrogen to encourage fruit development. Rice bran which has a nitrogen content of 2-6% can be used to produce nitrogen compounds (Maesaroh *et al.*, 2021).

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The average of 6.80 is the sago starch treatment (P4) which has the least average clusters per baglog. It could be that the lighting which is estimated to only reach 10% is still insufficient when the mushrooms emerge. Ten to fifteen percent illumination is needed while oyster mushrooms are growing in baglogs. However, direct sunlight entering the barn is not necessary for the fruiting body to develop on the surface of the media, it must first be exposed to light with a copying intensity of between 60 to 70 percent. This is because mushrooms need light stimulation to develop (Maesaroh *et al.*, 2021).

Wet Weight of Oyster Mushroom Fruit

Differences in the application of bran types have an impact on the moist weight of white oyster mushroom fruits. This is based on the findings of ANOVA analysis of variance. At an average wet weight of 152.78 grams, the wheat bran treatment (P3) had the largest oyster mushroom fruit average. Conversely, the rice bran treatment (P1) had the lowest average wet weight of oyster mushroom fruit. Similar results were also seen in the treatment of corn bran (P2) and sago starch (P4).

Wheat bran provides synthetic hormones to oyster mushrooms. Hormone administration Oyster mushrooms are given artificial hormones by using wheat bran. When artificial hormones are administered exogenously, the overall auxin activity increases. This results in larger shoot diameter and faster root growth, which in turn affects the wet weight of the fruit in white oyster mushrooms (Maula *et al.*, 2018).

It is evident that when compared to treatment with rice bran dosage, the results of treatment with rice bran dosage are very poor. This is due to the inability of rice bran to supply the nutrients required by white oyster mushrooms in the substrate. A certain ratio of nutrients can be provided; however, as the supply increases, the total amount of lignocellulose required for fungal development decreases, making wet weight a better and effective way to promote fungal growth. The amount of nutrients present in the growing medium that the mushroom is able to absorb will allow the mushroom to grow in wet weight. Environmental elements other than planting media greatly determine the growth of white oyster mushrooms so that they affect the wet weight of mushrooms (Syawal *et al.*, 2018).

CONCLUSIONS

The findings of the study revealed that the use of rice bran, corn bran, wheat bran, and sago starch had an effect on the mycelial growth rate and production rate of white oyster mushrooms. Treatment was found to be the most effective factor in influencing these parameters. P4 (sago starch), P3 (wheat bran), and P1 (rice bran).

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